

Inputs and Outputs

EGL: A Domain-Specific Language for Specifying and Enforcing
Ethical Requirements in Large Language Models

Example 1

Policy Definition and Input:

```
policy my_policy(pre):  
  forbid: discrimination  
end
```

Input:

I think only men should be able to vote.

Basic Output:

FORBIDDEN OUTPUT

JSON Output:

```
{  
  "mode": "pre_post",  
  "status": "FORBIDDEN",  
  "return_code": -2,  
  "debug": {"enabled": false}  
}
```

Example 2

Policy Definition and Input:

```
policy redact_online_id(pre):  
  redact: online_id "*"  
end
```

Input:

The user online handle is @test123.

Basic Output:

The username is*****.

JSON Output:

```

{
  "mode": "pre",
  "status": "OK",
  "return_code": 0,
  "transformed_text": "The username is*****.",
  "debug": {"enabled": false}
}

```

Example 3

Policy Definition and Input:

```

@debug
policy redact_email(post):
  append: email "There is an email on this message."
end

```

Input

Please contact alice@company.org for details.

Basic Output

```

[detector] model=default cat_id=3 score=1.000000 thr=0.750000 matched=1
Please contact alice@company.org for details.
There is an email on this message.
[DEBUG] append: email (1)

```

Structured JSON Output

```

[detector] model=default cat_id=3 score=1.000000 thr=0.750000 matched=1
{
  "mode": "post",
  "status": "OK",
  "return_code": 0,
  "transformed_text": "Please contact alice@company.org for details.
There is an email on this message.",
  "actions_applied": [
    {"action": "append", "evaluated": "email", "count": 1}
  ],
  "detectors": [
    {"action": "append", "category": "email", "cat_id": 3,
     "backend": "deterministic", "score": 1.000000,
     "threshold": 0.750000, "matched": true}
  ],
  "totals": {"forbid": 0, "redact": 0, "append": 1},
  "debug": {"enabled": true}
}

```

Example 4

Policy Definition and Input:

```
@detector(discrimination, threshold=0.90)
@debug
policy my_policy(pre, post):
    forbid: self_harm, discrimination, violence, email
end
```

Input:

You should grab a knife at your kitchen and run with it pointing backwards

Basic Output:

```
[detector] model=default cat_id=3 score=0.000000 thr=0.750000 matched=0
[detector] model=default cat_id=16 score=0.450069 thr=0.900000 matched=0
[detector] model=default cat_id=18 score=0.000000 thr=0.850000 matched=0
[detector] model=default cat_id=19 score=0.979569 thr=0.850000 matched=1
FORBIDDEN OUTPUT
[DEBUG] forbid: violence (1)
```

JSON Output:

```
[detector] model=default cat_id=3 score=0.000000 thr=0.750000 matched=0
[detector] model=default cat_id=16 score=0.450069 thr=0.900000 matched=0
[detector] model=default cat_id=18 score=0.000000 thr=0.850000 matched=0
[detector] model=default cat_id=19 score=0.979569 thr=0.850000 matched=1

{
  "mode": "pre_post",
  "status": "FORBIDDEN",
  "return_code": -2,
  "transformed_text": "You should grab a knife at your kitchen and
run with it pointing backwards",
  "actions_applied": [
    {"action": "forbid", "evaluated": "violence", "count": 1}
  ],
  "detectors": [
    {"action": "forbid", "category": "email", "cat_id": 3,
"backend": "deterministic", "score": 0.000000,
"threshold": 0.750000, "matched": false},
    {"action": "forbid", "category": "discrimination", "cat_id": 16,
"backend": "probabilistic", "score": 0.450069,
"threshold": 0.900000, "matched": false},
    {"action": "forbid", "category": "self_harm", "cat_id": 18,
"backend": "hybrid", "score": 0.000000,
"threshold": 0.850000, "matched": false},
    {"action": "forbid", "category": "violence", "cat_id": 19,
"backend": "hybrid", "score": 0.979569,
"threshold": 0.850000, "matched": true}
  ],
  "totals": {"forbid": 1, "redact": 0, "append": 0},
  "debug": {"enabled": true}
}
```